

DPP STANDARDISATION INITIATIVES & PROJECTS AROUND THE WORLD (V1.1)

25/06/2026

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the GA No 101158775. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2
S
S
A
P
R
C

Work package	WP6
Version	1.0
Authors	Anh Dao (e Circular ApS), Heino Claussen-Markefka (VDE e.V. DKE), Marvin Böll (VDE e.V. DKE), Rembrandt Koppelarr (ECO WISE), Carolynn Bernier (CEA)
Reviewers	
Abstract	This report presents a selection of Digital Product Passport (DPP) initiatives worldwide that are considered relevant to EU DPP and CIRPASS-2 standardization analysis. It also provides contextual background on the types of standardization bodies, basic of standards, and the criteria used to select the initiatives included. The objective is to raise awareness of standardization activities beyond the EU by providing a high-level overview. This is an ongoing effort and will be updated as needed.
Keywords	Digital product passport, DPP, standard, standardisation
Citation	Dao, A., Claussen-Markefka, H., Böll, M., Koppelaar, R., & Bernier, C. (2026). DPP STANDARDISATION INITIATIVES & PROJECTS AROUND THE WORLD. CIRPASS-2 consortium. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20271014

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
1.0	30/04/2026	Creation	
1.1	25/06/2026	Updated	

CIRPASS-2 CONSORTIUM

#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	Commissariat A L'Energie Atomique Et Aux Energies Alternatives	CEA	France
2	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool	TALTECH	Estonia
3	Mindworks Industries Ou	MWX	Estonia
4	DIGITALEUROPE AISBL	DIGITALEUROPE	Belgium
5	E CIRCULAR APS	E CIRCULAR APS	Denmark
6	F6s Network Ireland Limited	F6S IE	Ireland
7	Global Textile Scheme GmbH	GTS	Germany
8	maki Consulting GmbH	MAKI	Germany
9	Ekodenge Muhendislik Mimarlik Danismanlik Ticaret Anonim Sirketi	EKODENGE	Sweden
10	Stiftelsen Chalmers Industriteknik	CIT	Sweden
11	Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO	TNO	Netherlands
12	BIO Innovation Service SAS	BIOIS	France
13	Technische Universiteit DELFT	TU Delft	Netherlands
14	Asociacion De Empresas Tecnologicas INNOVALIA	INNOVALIA	Spain
15	CBT Comunicacion & Multimedia SL	CBT	Spain
16	Asociacion Para Desarrollo De La Economia Del Dato	BAIDATA	Spain
17	GS1 In Europe	GS1 IN EUROPE	Belgium
18	AOC Innovation	AOC INNOVATION	France
19	+IMPAKT Luxembourg SARL	+IMPAKT	Luxembourg
20	Industrie 4.0 Osterreich - Die Plattform Fur Intelligente Produktion	PIA	Austria
21	FUJITSU Technology Solutions	FJBE	Belgium
22	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung EV	Fraunhofer	Germany
23	Extra Red SRL	EXTRA RED SRL	Italy
24	European Apparel And Textile Confederation Aisbl	EURATEX	Belgium
25	IOXIO OY	IOXIO OY	Finland
26	Suomen Tekstiili Ja Muoti Ry	FINATEX	Finland
27	KEZZLER AS	Kezzler	Norway
28	EON Cloud Technology KFT	EON	Hungary
29	Avery Dennison Atma GmbH	atma.io	Austria
30	Circular.Fashion UG	circ.fashion	Germany
31	TRIPLER	TripleR	Belgium

32	SCANTRUST BV	SCANTRUST BV	Netherlands
33	ARCELIK A.S.	ARCELIK	Türkiye
34	WHATT.IO AB	whatt.io	Sweden
35	Gorenje Gospodinski Aparati DOO	GORENJE	Slovenia
36	Manufacture Francaise Des Pneumatiques MICHELIN	MICHELIN	France
37	COBUILDER AS	COBUILDER	Norway
38	DIN Deutsches Institut Fuer Normung EV	DIN e.V.	Germany
39	VDE Verband Der Elektrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik EV	VDE	Germany
40	Energy Web AG	Energy Web AG	Switzerland
41	WORLDLINE France	WORLDLINE FR	France
42	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt	PTB	Germany
43	Digital Data Chain Consortium GbR	DDCC	Germany
44	ZVEI e. V.	ZVEI e.V.	Germany
45	Association of Service and Computer Dealers International	ASCDI	US
46	Open Blockchain for Asset Disposition Alliance (OBADA)	OBADA	US
47	Green Electronics Council	GEC	US
48	Textile Exchange	TextileExchange	US
49	iPoint-Systems GmbH	iPoint	Germany

Grant Agreement No.: 101158775
Call: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04
Topic: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04-DIGIPASS
Type of action: DIGITAL Simple Grants

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union under the GA No 101158775. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© CIRPASS-2 Consortium, 2024-2027

Except otherwise noted, original content on this document is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence. This licence enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The licence allows for commercial use.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRDUCTION	7
2	STANDARDIZATION	9
2.1	Differences Between Standardization Organizations	9
2.2	Basics of Standards	9
2.2.1	The Unique Aspects of JTC24.....	10
3	SECTION: LANDSCAPE OF DPP STANDARDS	11
3.1	DPP-System Standards and Technical Specification Projects	11
IEC PC 132	Consistent and effective electronic labelling across industries	15
3.2	DPP-Data Standard Projects.....	22
4	CONCLUSION	28

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1: : CHARACTERISTICS OF VARIOUS STANDARDIZATION PROJECTS.....	12
TABLE 2: PROJECTS RELATED TO DPP-SYSTEM STANDARDS AND TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS AND PROJECTS.....	13
TABLE 3 : STANDARDS, SPECIFICATIONS AND PROJECTS ON DPP DATA.....	22

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
DPP	Digital Product Passport
CDB	Consortium-based Standard Bodies
CEN	Comité Européen de Normalisation
CENELEC	Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique
CWA	Workshop Agreement
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
GSO	Government-recognized Standardization Organization
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JTC	Joined Technical Committee
PWI	Preliminary Work Item
SDO	Standards Developing Organization
TC	Technical Committee
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNTP	UN Transparency Protocol
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WG	Working Group

1 INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly digital world, increasingly more data must be associated with objects (products). This linked product data is assigned using unique identifiers and tags. This initially rather generic concept was incorporated as the so-called Digital Product Passport (DPP), a central element of Regulation (EU) 2024/1781, also known as the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR).

It is therefore understandable that numerous academic and industrial bodies, conferences, and research institutions have been intensively engaged with the topic of linked object data and the various forms of digital product passports in recent years. This engagement and discussion of the topic is not limited to the EU and specific industries but has taken place on an international and cross-industry basis.

Amidst this momentum, it is helpful to establish a better understanding of the similarities and differences among these different concepts under the name of DPP in terms of scope, requirements, and functionalities. This helps to raise awareness and generate discussion across the globe so that the concept of linked object data could act as an enabler to development and innovation, instead of a potential barrier to trade or unnecessary burden to businesses through authorities.

This report aims to provide an overview of initiatives and projects by official recognized international and national standardization organizations or standardization consortia with a view to defining the requirements for DPP concepts. The goal is to determine to what extent, beyond the framework defined by the ESPR, other DPP concepts exist that have similar scopes of application or employ comparable technical concepts. This is intended to assist in assessing the extent to which the European Commission's stated goal of achieving the most comprehensive interoperability possible for the EU-DPP will be realized.

The European Commission has tasked European standardization organizations with developing a normative framework for the EU-DPP system which was carried out by the Joint Technical Committee 24 (JTC24) of CEN/CENELEC. A key requirement is ensuring cross-sector and cross-system interoperability. The details of this task are described in the standardization request and include, among other things, the following system categories:

- Unique identifiers
- Data carriers and links between physical product and digital representation
- Access rights management, information, system security, and business confidentiality
- Interoperability (technical, semantic, organization)
- Data processing, data exchange protocols and data formats
- Data storage, archiving, and data persistence, data authentication, reliability, integrity
- Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for product passport lifecycle management and searchability

The initiatives and projects listed are based on publicly available information and are intended, where possible – in line with the ESPR approach – to describe the various aspects of a complete or nearly complete DPP system.

In the context of classification, a distinction is made between whether the initiatives and projects are standards, normative standards, or harmonized normative standards. Only harmonized normative standards, such as those developed CEN/CENELEC JTC24, have legally binding effects.

Furthermore, this report is not intended to express a preference for any particular concept or technical implementation, nor to draw conclusions regarding the interoperability, interchangeability, or completeness of the standards/protocols developed within the scope of these projects. This also applies to their potential compliance with EU DPP requirements, regardless of how closely these may align with the framework standards developed in JTC24.

For the list of other projects or initiatives working on individual areas of standardization similarly to those of JTC 24, please see the list from [CIRPASS results](#). This report will be updated regularly as new information becomes public or new initiatives are established. Feedback is welcome to ensure the project list is as complete and descriptions as accurate as possible.

Additionally, CIRPASS-2, with the support of its Expert Working Group 2, also are in contact or have liaisons with the various Standardization Organizations and consortia. The goal is to create a harmonized understanding of criteria for interoperable DPP frameworks among a wider range of audience. The efforts to establish contacts and exchange information with various organizations, consortia and initiatives is ongoing.

Assumptions and disclaimer: The mentioned standards are not endorsed or preferred to any specific standards. Bundle of standards that we perceived (based on current publicly available information), that are close to the EU vision of the DPP should not be compared with the standards developed by CEN/CENELEC JTC24, since the work of CEN/CENELEC JTC24 is not public at the time this report is released. An analysis of whether systems based on these standards have connectivity to the EU-DPP may be conducted at a later point of the project.

2 STANDARDIZATION

The following tables list a wide variety of initiatives and projects that – due to their status – have very different areas of influence. To better understand the varying impacts and significance of these different activities in relation to the digital product passport, it is first necessary to distinguish between the various types of standardization. Standards are being developed by Standardization Developing Organizations (SDO). There are several types of SDOs each with its own scope, method of working and degree of acceptance.

2.1 DIFFERENCES BETWEEN STANDARDIZATION ORGANIZATIONS

Government-recognized standardization organizations (GSOs) are authorized to develop standards that are valid at the national level. Typical examples of such standardization organizations include AFNOR / AFNOR - CEF in France and DIN / DKE in Germany etc. Just as there are nationally recognized standards organizations, there are also officially recognized standards organizations at the European (CEN/CENELEC and ETSI) and international (ISO/IEC and ITU) levels.

What all these organizations have in common is that they must adhere to strict rules and procedures in their work. However, the fact that the standards published by these organizations are issued as official standards does not mean that these standards automatically become legally binding. This always requires separate legal provisions in which laws and regulations are linked to the (technical) content of a standard. In the European context, this is called harmonization, and the standard thus linked to the European legal system is referred to as a “harmonized standard.”

Consortium-based standards bodies (CDBs) can be established by anyone or interest group. They typically consist of a clearly defined group of experts who often share similar interests. Since they are not initially bound by externally prescribed procedures and the consortia usually have a tight focus, these consortia often work more quickly and achieve more clearly defined results. Typical examples of such consortia include the IEEE, W3C, GS1, or all kind of industrial consortia. It is not uncommon for the results of such consortia to be incorporated, in whole or in part, into official standards at a later date.

Initiatives and projects launched by organizations are additional bodies involved in the development of standards. Typical examples include the UN Transparency Protocol (UNTP) of the UNCE and the Responsible Business Transparency Protocol (RBTP) of the Responsible Business Alliance and CIRPASS-2. It is quite difficult to provide a universal classification of these bodies, as they are structured very differently.

To understand and interpret the tables in this document, it is important to note that only standards issued by government - recognized standardization organizations can have legally binding effect through a specific designation (for Europe: “harmonized standard”).

2.2 BASICS OF STANDARDS

The fundamental principle of standardization is to gather the practical knowledge of users and industry stakeholders and consolidate it into a general specification. A key objective is to make these standards widely available, as their effectiveness and purpose are realized only through their broad applicability.

The description above shows that standardization is generally retrospective in nature, as it systematically captures experience and best practice knowledge regarding implemented solutions. For this reason, standards are typically developed by so-called (technical) committees composed of experts in the relevant fields. These experts are generally professionals from industry or the industrial sector.

These experts bring a wide range of experiences and perspectives to the table. Therefore, the selection and composition of (technical) committees are of crucial importance for the quality and transparency of the

results achieved. As a result of this recognition, most government-recognized standards organizations have clear and strict formal guidelines governing how experts are appointed to committees.

Other key characteristics of the process for developing normative standards include the fact that anyone can submit a standardization request, that decisions by technical committees must generally be reached by consensus, that there is a public objection procedure, and that publication follows a defined procedure. Consortium-based standardization bodies or projects are not required to adhere to all of these principles.

A common mistake made when considering standards is the assumption that they are a description of a technical solution or an engineering guide for a solution. This assumption leads in the wrong direction.

The standards published by government-recognized standards organizations represent a specification within which a (technical) solution must operate if it is to comply with the standard. Such standards therefore describe the boundaries within which the solution must operate, not how it should be (technically) implemented. Standards do not replace the requirements specification but rather specify which characteristics are to be achieved. The openness of standards regarding actual implementation is a central requirement of official standards, so as not to disadvantage any provider of solutions.

A good introduction to normative standards can be found here: <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/a-brief-introduction-to-standards>

2.2.1 THE UNIQUE ASPECTS OF JTC24

It is not unusual for the European Commission to issue standardization mandates to European standardization organizations. The establishment of CEN/CENELEC JTC24 is based on the Commission's Implementing Decision of July 31, 2024 (C(2024) 5423 final). More than 250 experts in numerous working groups then set out to describe these requirements in eight standards.

Nevertheless, the standardization process surrounding the Digital Product Passport (DPP) has some distinctive features that must be taken into account when evaluating the process and comparing it with other international initiatives. The key ones are listed below:

- Unlike a typical case, CEN/CENELEC JTC24's standardization mandate does not involve compiling a comprehensive description of the current state of the art, but rather developing standards to implement the concept of the digital product passport – a concept that is new in nature and driven by political and regulatory factors.
- Compared to other standardization processes and taking into account the established procedures, the 18-month timeframe set by the Commission was very ambitious.
- To ensure the standards' legal effectiveness quickly, the harmonization process – which normally proceeds sequentially – was carried out in parallel.
- The standardization mandate applied only to certain components of the so-called DPP system. Other key components, such as the registry or the required data, were not included in the standardization mandate.
- By the time the standardization project was completed, key issues that were to be defined within the framework of the so-called delegated acts – such as those regarding user groups and rights – remained unresolved.

3 SECTION: LANDSCAPE OF DPP STANDARDS

This section gives a preliminary overview of the various emerging DPP standardisation projects around the world, where the focus is on Standardization of the DPP System and DPP-Data. The section includes initiatives and projects of international and national, standardization Consortia or projects and initiatives with relation to defining the requirements of DPP.

As described in Section 2, the objectives, composition, and procedures of the various bodies can vary greatly, and it is difficult to establish scientifically sound and precise criteria for distinguishing between them. Therefore, this overview does not claim to be exhaustive. Rather, it is intended to highlight which other initiatives are known and how they are structured. Due to space constraints, a detailed comparison of the individual activities cannot be provided here. Additionally, to facilitate the categorization of the various activities, they have been classified into specific types. The types are described in **Table 1**. The landscape may serve as a basis for a further gap analysis in the standardization landscape.

Standards that are not focused on DPPs but on other topics are not covered in the mapping scope here, even if they are utilized within DPP related standards. We are only interested in standards that are specifically used for DPP contexts. CEN workshop agreements (CWA) are not mapped here and neither are UN Recommendations.

3.1 DPP-SYSTEM STANDARDS AND TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION PROJECTS

For the mapping of the DPP standards, 5 aspects are being considered:

- **Project:** Projects focused on the development of Standards for DPP frameworks
- **Type:** This column indicates the type of standardization project. The following types are considered:
 - a) Official Standardisation Request (result: legal binding normative standard)
 - b) Formal Standardisation Request (result: normative standard, technical report or specification)
 - c) Consortium Standardisation Projekt (result: standard, specifications etc.)
 - d) Research Projects that consider standardization of DPP frameworks (result: depending on the scope)
- **Technical Committee:** This Column list the Technical Committee and its responsible Working Group
- **Scope:** Short Description of the Objective and Scope of the Project
- **Additional Remarks:** May include additional information, such as Status, Amendments etc.

TABLE 1: CHARACTERISTICS OF VARIOUS STANDARDIZATION PROJECTS

#	Type of Request	Triggered by Whom?	Committee Structure	Result	Formal Procedure	Legal Binding Effect	Required to
a)	harmonized Standard	Legislator	Groups of experts intended to fully represent the state of the art Organized by GSOs	Official, harmonized Standard	Yes, a must	Yes, but separate legal act is required in any way	Neutrality
b)	normative Standard	Everybody	Groups of experts intended to fully represent the state of the art Organized by GSOs	Official Standard	Yes, a must	Not in general, but legal effects may occur	Neutrality
c)	Application focussed	Interest Group	Groups of experts focused on the objective Organized by Interest Group	Consortia Standard	Optional, depending on consortium	No	on the objective
d)	Addressing specific Tasks	Project Groups / Initiatives	Depending on the project / objective Organized by Project Gr	Depending on the Scope	Usually not	No	on the objective

TABLE 2: PROJECTS RELATED TO DPP-SYSTEM STANDARDS AND TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS AND PROJECTS

PROJECTS	TYPE	TECHNICAL COMMITTEE	SCOPE	REMARK / STATUS
<p>EN 18219 - DPP - Unique identifiers</p> <p>rEN 18220 – DPP - Data carriers</p> <p>EN 18216 – DPP - Data exchange protocols</p> <p>EN 18222 – DPP - Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for the product passport lifecycle management and searchability</p> <p>EN 18223 – DPP -System interoperability</p> <p>EN 18221 – DPP -data storage, archiving, and data persistence</p> <p>prEN 18239 – DPP - access rights management, information system security, and business confidentiality</p> <p>prEN 18246 – DPP - Data authentication, reliability and integrity</p>	<p>Type a)</p> <p>EU Standard</p>	<p>CEN/CLC JTC 24</p>	<p>The scope of these Standards addresses the technical requirements to address the regulatory requirements from the ESPR. Developed by the CEN/CLC JTC24, these Standards cover the 8 DPP-System aspects.</p>	<p>Publication:</p> <p>Q2 2026</p>

<p>Digital Product Passport - Dictionary referencing: Concepts and principles</p> <p>N 458</p>	<p>Type a)</p> <p>EU standard</p>	<p>CEN/CLC/JTC24 WG 4</p> <p>Interoperability framework</p>	<p>This document provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A specification of the technical solution for referencing dictionaries across sectors and different product specific dictionaries from a DPP - A definition of the process for referencing the dictionaries - A definition of the criteria for referencing a dictionary (i.e. requirements for dictionaries) <p>This document focuses on data defined in delegated acts and harmonised standards. This document addresses the requirements on repositories listed in EN 18223</p>	<p>Work item is proposed, not approved yet</p>
<p>N/A</p>	<p>Type a) or b)</p> <p>International Level</p>	<p>ISO/IEC JTC5 - DPP</p>	<p>The ISO/IEC JTC5 is tasked with the Development of deliverables for the deployment of Digital Product Passports (DPP) and the data delivering ecosystem while ensuring cross sectoral and cross system interoperability.</p> <p>This JTC does not develop sector specific standards and standards to be used for DPP-system or DPP-data which are already covered by</p>	<p>Kick-Off: September 2026</p>

			the scope of other ISO and IEC TCs	
IEC 63700 ED1	Type b) Int. Standard	IEC PC 132 Consistent and effective electronic labelling across industries	<p>The scope of this project committee for electronic labels includes requirements and guidance for encapsulating product data and providing that information electronically, Specifications for electronic labelling and requirements and guidance on how to integrate electronic labels into products.</p> <p>Electronic labelling is intended for use by consumers, manufacturers, designers, and authorities having jurisdictions.</p> <p>Not included in the scope are the prescription of the content of the electronic label, but rather is designed to promote the use of consistent and effective electronic labelling practices across a broad range of sectors and products. An electronic label is intended to be machine readable. The electronic label has information embedded in it or is a pointer to the electronic storage location or combination</p>	Publication Q2 2027
PWI Digital Product Passport Part 1 –	Type b) Int. Standard	ISO/TC 154/ JWG 9 Processes, data elements and documents	This ISO/UNECE joint working group works on information	ISO 25534-1 passed the NP ballot in January 2026,

Overview and fundamental principles		in commerce, industry and administration	exchange of supply chain aligned to UN/CEFACT semantics Define fundamental Principles for global interoperability	but ISO unilaterally decided to put it on hold. On the UNECE-UN/CEFACT side, the joint project was approved as the UNECE-UN/CEFACT P1143 GDPP project in December 2025.
ISO 20435 “A Framework for Representing Physical Assets using Tokens”	Type b) Int. Standard	ISO/TC 307 / WG8	This standard is only one component of the DPP: This standard establishes a DLT agnostic, decentralized identifier (DID) framework for representing physical assets using tokens, which includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A DID generation method • A cryptographic method to tie asset data objects to the DID • A DID method scheme • Real world trust anchor processes 	
ISO 23726 Industrial automation systems and integration — Ontology based interoperability	Type b) Int. Standard	ISO/TC 184/SC 4 (Industrial data) https://www.iso.org/committees/54158.html	Industrial automation systems and integration – Ontology based interoperability (OBI)	Multi-part standard, currently under development
ECE/TRADE/C/CEFACT/2024/6	Type b) Int. Level Guide	UNECE	UNTP recommendation that enables transparency over global supply-chains. It aims to solve the	Currently under development.

<p>UNECE / UNTP: United Nations Transparency Protocol</p>		<p>https://uncefact.github.io/spec-untp/docs/about/</p> <p>https://untp.unece.org/</p>	<p>problem related to the multiplicity of traceability platforms, separates product data from claims related to the data (using verifiable credentials), enables selective data sharing and aims for low-cost implementation.</p> <p>protocol, not a platform, meaning that it focuses on interoperability standards that allow any technology platform to participate in interoperable and sustainable value chains.)</p>	<p>V0.7 of base data models available, V0.7 of the complete protocol expected for public review end of March 2026.</p>
<p>IEEE P3828 Standard for Digital Product Passport – Reference Architecture and Technical Requirements</p>	<p>Type c) Int. Consortium Standard</p>	<p>IEEE CTS/DFESC - Digital Finance and Economy Standards Committee</p>	<p>The scope of proposed standard covers the specification of a basic framework for digital product passport (DPP) which is a structured collection of product related, machine-readable data describing scope, data management scheme and access rights. DPP is conveyed through a unique product identifier accessible via electronic means through a data carrier. The standard provides the technical requirements for the indicator system, technical benchmarks, and management requirements</p>	<p>Lead by China (CAICT)</p>
<p>ASTM WK96018 Revision of E3461-25 Standard Guide for Principles of Circular Product Design</p>	<p>Type b) National US standard</p>	<p>Subcommittee: E60.13</p>	<p>circular product design principles applicable at each stage of the circular product life cycle, including material acquisition, production and manufacturing, use and consumption, and end-of-use. The</p>	

<p>ASTM WK95902 Revision of E3461-25 Standard Guide for Principles of Circular Product Design</p>			<p>addition of detailed principles will offer further pragmatic guidance for designers on how to implement each principle during the design process, tailored to the distinct requirements of each life cycle phase. Each principle will include a statement describing it and a rationale explaining why a designer may consider it during circular product design. The potential triple bottom line benefits (i.e., economic, environmental, and social) from implementing each principle will also be included through this revision. Furthermore, several examples demonstrating the application of each principle to different products will be incorporated into the guide to help designers and organizations understand how to practically apply these principles.</p>	
<p>GS1 Circularity - Digital Product Passport</p>	<p>Type c) Int. Consortium</p>	<p>GS1</p>	<p>Launch of WG aimed to identify an addressing structure in the GS1 domain able to fulfill EU DPP requirements in terms of traceability in the value chain. At the end, they want to adapt GS1 addressing system to EU DPP requirements</p>	
<p>W3C Verifiable Credentials Working Group</p>	<p>Type c) Int. Consortium</p>	<p>W3C</p>	<p>Adoption of new charter to develop deliverables for vocabularies for EU DPP and EU Business Wallet.</p>	<p>https://www.w3.org/2026/03/vc-wg-charter.html</p>

			Corresponds to JTC-24 modules 4, 5 and 7.	
NEMA-DPP	Type c) National US level	DPP	N/A	NEMA Roadmap Regional Consortial Standards
T/CABC 13—2024 Digital product passport — Unique coding for traction battery	Type b) or c) National Chinese Standard	CABC	Battery	http://www.cabc.net.cn/Standards/929.shtml
Various projects with relevance to DPP System aspects	Type b) International level standards	IEC TC 65	The Scope of IEC TC65 is to prepare international standards for systems and elements used for industrial process measurement, control and automation. To coordinate standardization activities which affect integration of components and functions into such systems including safety and security aspects. This work of standardization is to be carried out in the international fields for equipment and systems	https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:30:2583424270756:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1250,25
General requirements for Digital Product Passports (DPP) GB/T 20251568-T-469	Type b) National Chinese Standard	TC 267 originally, now linked to SWG41 - National Digital Product Passport Standardisation Working Group hosted by ANCC	1. General Principles: This document sets out the fundamental principles for establishing a Digital Product Passport (DPP), including compliance, transparency, unique identification, pre-defined requirements, comprehensive supply chain, and cost-effectiveness.	Standard link https://std.samr.gov.cn/gb/search/gbDetailed?id=1CB92886179AEDB9E06397BE0A0A064B Committee setup with 43 experts dec 2025

				Committee link: https://std.samr.gov.cn/search/orgDetailView?data_id=49E1A142AD943A89E06397BE0A0A9977
“DPP” Project	Type b) National Chinese Project	CAICT Technical Lead: MIIT	National System for DPPs (e.g Battery Textiles)	
“DPP” Project for traceability of car components (e.g Battery)	Type b) National Chinese Project	CATARC Under SAC	National System for development DPPs	
ITU-T Y.DPP.TRUST Trust framework for DPP systems supporting IoT enabled product lifecycle data management	Type b) International standard	ITU	Trust framework for digital product passport systems supporting IoT-enabled product lifecycle data management. The standard will explore how to verify the identity and permissions of DPP-related entities, how to ensure the authenticity and traceability of DPP data during generation, updating, and use, how to support trusted lifecycle management, and how to achieve reliable association between physical products and DPP systems, based on four dimensions: entity trust, data trust, process trust, and technology trust	Press release: https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/vWgwpcjNOAHxgJUAEBuukg DPP4EU presentation ITU
ITU-T Y. DPP.ICT Requirements and System Architecture of Digital	Type b)	ITU	Linking ICT goods to their digital passports across the full life cycle (manufacturing to end-of-life)	DPP4EU presentation ITU

Product Passport for ICT goods	International standard			https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/workprog/wp_item.aspx?isn=23507
ITU-T YSTR.OS-DPP-ICT A case study of an open-source Digital Product Passport system for ICT goods use case	Type b Technical report	ITU		DPP4EU presentation ITU

3.2 DPP-DATA STANDARD PROJECTS

This chapter provides an overview of the Standards and Projects focussing on the DPP Data.

TABLE 3 : STANDARDS, SPECIFICATIONS AND PROJECTS ON DPP DATA

Projects	Type	Technical Committee	Scope	Sector	Remarks
<p>ETSI ES 204 082</p> <p>Environmental Engineering (EE); An information model for digital product information on sustainability and circularity</p> <p>It is published respectively by ITU and ETSI as Recommendation ITU-T L.1071 [i.44] and ETSI ES 204 082 (the present document),</p>	<p>Type b)</p> <p>EU level</p>	<p>ETSI TC EE and ITU-T Study Group 5</p> <p>https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_es/204000_204099/204082/01.01.00_50/es_204082v010100m.pdf</p>	<p>Very Similar: Matching scope. This reflects EU ESPR and surrounding work but framed for global DPP system.</p>	Telecom.	
<p>Product circularity Data sheet</p>	<p>Type b)</p> <p>International Level</p>	ISO TC 323 WG5	Circularity information	Sector-agnostic	

<p>"Textile Product Digital Passport Part 1: General Principles" (Plan No.: 202406-CNTAC01)</p>	<p>Type c) National Chinese Level</p>	<p>Association standard CNTAC</p>			<p>Released December 2025 Published January 2026 https://www.ttbz.org.cn/standardDetail/45tq145bqd5608zqigm7heh9t0tkgtw.html</p>
<p>"Textile Product Digital Passport Part 2: Definition of Terms" (Plan No.: 202406-CNTAC02)</p>	<p>Type c) National Chinese Level</p>	<p>Association standard CNTAC</p>		<p>Textile</p>	<p>Released December 2025 Published January 2026 https://www.ttbz.org.cn/standardDetail/1bnc7gq67ifa9lyaar4ab0ugnwknsnp.html</p>

<p>"Textile Product Digital Passport Part 3: Labeling Technical Specifications" (Plan No.: 202406-CNTAC03)</p>	<p>Type c) National Chinese Level</p>	<p>Association standard CNTAC</p>			<p>Released December 2025 Published January 2026 https://www.ttbz.org.cn/standardDetail/4688am66talpzaeihtrkmbd5xy2omz.html</p>
<p>"Textile Product Digital Passport Part 4: Coding rules"</p>	<p>Type c) National Chinese Level</p>	<p>Association standard CNTAC</p>		<p>http://js.cnr.cn/rdzt/qnjs/qnjsgdwx/20250403/t20250403_527122770.shtml</p>	
<p>T/CTES Standard Project Proposal for "Digital Passport Requirements for Quality, Safety, Functionality and Comfort of Summer Functional Fabrics"</p>	<p>Type c) National Chinese Level</p>	<p>CTES association standard</p>		<p>Textile https://www.ctes.com.cn/ttbz/GZZX/art/2025/art_f3b2bdd1aae446895f28d6fc01113f8.html</p>	
<p>2. T/CTES Standard Project Proposal for "Requirements for Digital Passports for Textile Environmental Footprint Products"</p>	<p>Type c) National Chinese Level</p>	<p>CTES association standard</p>		<p>Textile https://www.ctes.com.cn/ttbz/GZZX/art/2025/art_f3b2bdd1aae446895f28d6fc01113f8.html</p>	

3. T/CTES Standard Project Proposal for "Requirements for Digital Passports for Textile Recyclability Products"	Type c) National Chinese Level	CTES association standard		Textile https://www.ctes.com.cn/ttbz/GZZX/art/2025/art_f3b2bdd1aae446895f28d6fc01113f8.html	
4. T/CTES Standard Project Proposal for "Textile ESG Product Digital Passport Requirements"	Type c) National Chinese Level	CTES association standard		Textile https://www.ctes.com.cn/ttbz/GZZX/art/2025/art_f3b2bdd1aae446895f28d6fc01113f8.html	
ISO/AWI 25737-1 Prefabricated Building — Application of Digital Product Passport (DPP) in construction industry Part 1: Principles for modular product application	Type b) International - Level	ISO	This document specifies a set of principles for application of Digital Product Passport(DPP)in modular product throughout its lifecycle, including application methodologies, application technical frameworks, overall application requirements, and application evaluation. This documents also provide examples for DPP application.	Construction https://www.iso.org/standard/91355.html Secretariat: China	
T/CIAPS0049-2025 Battery Passport Guidance	Type c) National Chinese Level	CIAPS association standard	This document provides information disclosure guidelines for battery traceability data management throughout its life cycle, aiming to guide companies in the production and	Batteries	Finished and published

		China Industrial Association of Power Sources	management of battery products. A battery passport is created to facilitate traceability management of battery products. This document applies to electric vehicle batteries, light transport vehicle batteries, industrial batteries with energy greater than 2 kWh, portable batteries, and batteries for other purposes.	https://www.ciaps.org.cn/	
J3327_202509 - Electric Vehicle (EV) Battery Traceability Record	Type c) International Level	SAE International	This standard centers on establishing a consistent, globally recognized practice for Electric Vehicle Battery data collection that is the foundation of an audit trail and independent verification within the EV Battery supply chain. This practice also supports Reuse and Recycling.	Batteries https://www.sae.org/standards/j3327_202509-electric-vehicle-ev-battery-traceability-record	https://doi.org/10.4271/J3327_202509
Technical Requirements for DPPs of Light Industry Products	Type c) National Chinese Level	CNLIC China Light Industry Council	Technical scope, basic architecture, data collection requirements for product data, quality information, Traceability, carbon footprint	Light Industry Products (appliances, furniture, food, paper, light industry machines, daily chemicals, leather) https://www.clii.com.cn/ReDianJuJiao/TouTiaoXinWin/202511/t20251126_3960350.html	Application of experts until April 2026

--	--	--	--	--	--

4 CONCLUSION

The purpose of this report is to provide an overview of international standardization activities related to the DPP. It is evident that this topic is receiving significant attention worldwide. It is also evident that the number of organizations, projects, and approaches dealing with the topic of DPP varies widely. In this initial report on the subject, the sheer volume of identified projects made it impossible to conduct a detailed analysis or comparison of the various approaches and projects. This may be a task for subsequent projects.

However, what is already clear from the list is that, in addition to an analysis of the content, an assessment of the type of standardization and its legal relevance is also important. Significant differences can already be identified here. The highly regulatory concept of the digital product passport, initiated by the European Commission and described in the ESPR, requires legally binding (harmonized) standards for its implementation.

These were developed within the framework of a Joint Technical Committee (JTC 24), although the process involved in this procedure has some distinctive features compared to other standardization procedures. These are outlined in the report to facilitate a clearer definition and classification of the procedure. A similar initiative driven by legislators does not yet appear to be emerging on the international stage.